

Improving Fish and Shrimp Health and Performance with Halophyte Bioactives

Aquaculture increasingly demands **natural feed ingredients** that can **support animal health and performance while reducing reliance on antibiotics and chemical treatments**. Bacterial diseases, stress, and inflammation remain major challenges in fish and shrimp production, directly affecting welfare, growth and production efficiency.

In IGNITION, **salt-tolerant plants such as purple glasswort (*Salicornia ramosissima*) have been explored as a source of bioactive-rich, sustainable feed ingredients**. Grown on saline or marginal land, they do not compete for freshwater or arable land used for conventional crops, and their biomass can be valorised across different bio-based industries.

Results obtained so far indicate bioactive extracts are **compatible with existing feed production and feeding strategies**, have **strong bactericidal activity against key aquaculture pathogens** including *Vibrio* spp., *Tenacibaculum*

maritimum, and *Photobacterium* spp., **immune-enhancing and anti-inflammatory properties**, and the **potential to support improvements in production performance**.

Control of key aquaculture pathogens

Bioactives EXT3, XAD, and FREM consistently **reduced the percentage of live pathogens** at all tested dosages, indicating their potential to **mitigate disease outbreaks** and **support strategies to lower antibiotic and chemical use**.

Immune-enhancing potential

White leg shrimp fed diets supplemented with bioactives EXT3 and XAD generally revealed **increased concentration of haemolymph proteins**, which serve critical roles in immunity, including the recognition and killing of pathogens, redox regulation, coagulation, and melanisation, indicating the **immune-enhancing potential of halophyte bioactives, particularly under acute air exposure stress conditions**.

Support for improvement in production performance

Fish fed on diets supplemented with EXT3 and/or XAD and exposed to pathogen infection or transport-induced stress revealed **slight enhancements in growth** (Atlantic salmon) and **intestinal amino acid transport** (European seabass), the latter with relevance for nutrient utilization, indicating the **potential of bioactives for performance improvement or maintenance under stress conditions**.

European seabass 24 h post transport stress

Atlantic salmon 72 h post Yersinia ruckeri infection

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